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Appendix 1: Midterm report

Exploring Iris.ai and Yewn with Think-Aloud tests: a mid-term perspective.

AI & research support: Literature search

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Dansk resumé

Artificial intelligence (AI) er et felt inden for informationsvidenskab, som er i hastig udvikling og deraf bundet denne rapport i hvorvidt og i hvilken retning AI kan supportere forskere og studerende i litteratursøgninger og litteratursynteser på universitetet. Dette fokus er især i forhold til den voksende mængde artikler og data, der dagligt bliver større på tværs af samtlige fagområder som Det Kongelige Bibliotek (KB) servicere. AI har potentialet til at analysere store mængder komplekse tekst korpora og via matematiske formler, at eftergøre menneskers måde at lære, træffe beslutninger og løse problemer på. Til gengæld kan opgaven oftest udføres med en hastighed og nøjagtighed, der langt overstiger et menneskes evne. Men alt dette kræver større krav til træningen af brugere og en synlig detaljeringsgrad i forhold til hvordan AI software fungerer i forhold til litteraturforskning, dens transparens, validitet og reliabilitet, da værktøjerne, der er tilgængelige via biblioteket skal understøtte en akademisk tilgang til litteratursøgninger. Akademisk søgning forstås som søgemetoder hvor gennemsigtighed, reproducerbarhed, dokumentation og pålidelighed er nøglen for at sikre det altafgørende i en søgeproces: effektivitet, troværdighed, kvalitet, pålidelighed.

Formålet med denne rapport er at sammenfatte brugeroplevelsen og ydeevnen af to AI-søgesystemer på baggrund af flere tænke-højt tests. Rapporten arbejder med mål og forskningsspørgsmål som bundet i hvordan ovenstående faktorer for akademisk søgning understøttes af AI systemerne og om – eller hvordan disse systemer kan skabe værdi for henholdsvis brugere og informationsspecialister. Vi har en arbejdshypotese i projektet om, at forskellige typer brugere (studerende, seniorforskere og bibliotekspersonale) lægger forskellige værdier i forskellige former for support og at vi med disse tests vil få belyst hvilke værdier og hvilken vej inden for vores biblioteksservices vi ønsker at gå.

Forskningsspørgsmål:

- Hvordan understøtter de AI-drevne søgesystemer Iris.ai og Yewno Discover en akademisk søgning, hvor værdier som effektivitet, troværdighed, kvalitet, pålidelighed, dokumentation og gennemsigtighed i et system er altafgørende?
- Hvilken værdi fjerner Iris.ai og Yewno til den akademiske søgeproces for brugere?
- Hvilken værdi fjerner Iris.ai og Yewno til den akademiske søgeproces for informationsfagfolk?

De to AI systemer, der er blevet testet, er Iris.ai og Yewno. Testene blev foretaget i perioden april til maj 2021. Testpersonerne var informationsspecialister, der hands-on i systemerne udforskede om – og hvordan funktionaliteten i systemerne understøtter akademiske søgemetoder og handlinger. 9 informationsspecialister deltog i tænke-højt testene. Fem tests i Iris.ai og fire i Yewno blev afholdt på henholdsvis universitetsbibliotekerne i Aarhus og København. To moderatorer kørte hver test. Den ene var moderator og førte dialogen og guidede testpersonen gennem de opgaver, der var beskrevet i tænke-højt-testen. Den anden tester noterede testpersoners adfærd, reaktioner og kommentarer. Alle tests blev dokumenteret ved hjælp af Zoom-optagelser. Testene var delt i tre dele – 1) Præinterview af testpersonen for at få viden om deres ekspertise indenfor informationssøgning samt eventuel AI-drevet teknologisk kunnen, 2) Hands-on søgningerne i det AI-drevne søgesystem ved hjælp af den samme case-opgave. Testpersonen "tænkte højt" undervejs og 3) Postinterview af testpersonen med refleksionsspørgsmål i forhold til søgningen og tilfredshed med systemet

De fleste testpersoner beskrev Yewno som et opdagelsesværktøj. Den primære funktionalitet i Yewno er at udforske et emne frem for at være et værktøj, der understøtter akademisk litteratursøgning. Selvom Yewno ikke blev betragtet som understøttende for en *systematisk* tilgang til søgning, påpegede testpersonerne, at Yewno godt kunne spille en supplerende rolle i den akademiske litteratursøgningsproces. Alle var enige om, at det kunne være nyttigt ved projektstart at udforske mere om et forskningsspørgsmål, undersøge begreber, få overblik over indbyrdes forhold og mulige retninger i et forskningsområde og gennem serendipitet opdage nye og uventede begreber og relationer. Ligeledes fik den sømløse bevægelse fra det søgte begreb til fuldtekst af relevante artikler meget ros. Eksport- og dokumentations muligheder blev kritiseret for manglende tilpasningsmuligheder og en interaktiv søgehistorik var savnet. Testpersonerne blev bedt om at bedømme deres overordnede tilfredshed med Yewno på en skala fra 1 til 5 (5 er højeste/bedste bedømmelse), og den samlede tilfredsheds score for Yewno var 3.

Den samlede oplevelse af Iris.ai bundede i at testpersonerne som udgangspunkt godt kunne lide systemets design, men de var skuffede over systemets manglende funktionalitet til at hjælpe med at sortere, filtrere og evaluere relevansen af det fundne materiale. Dette gjorde testpersonerne mistroiske over kvaliteten af Iris.ai. Stor forventning til strukturerede og avancerede søgninger gjorde testpersonerne frustrerede, fordi Iris.ai viste sig at være mere *'eksplorativ'*. I så fald så testpersonerne det som et nyttigt supplement til andre databaser. Flertallet mente, at tillid til resultatet kræver ekspertviden om både emnet og Iris.ai. Ydermere ville det være meget tidskrævende at opnå færdigheder i Iris.ai. Testpersonerne blev bedt om at reflektere over evnen til at dokumentere deres arbejde i Iris.ai. Kun få var tilfredse med dokumentationen i forbindelse med deres søgning. Alle testpersoner fandt det skuffende, at de ikke kunne eksportere deres søgeresultat og referencer direkte til andre referenceprogrammer end Zotero. De var imidlertid tilfredse med mulighederne i Iris.ai for at eksportere til CSV og Excel. Dataene i de eksporterede filer var tilfredsstillende, men nogle ønskede, at Iris.ai også ville eksportere indholdet fra de fremsøgte *topics*. Tilfredshedsbedømmelserne var igen på en skala fra 1 til 5 (5 er højeste/bedste bedømmelse), og den samlede tilfredsheds score for Iris.ai var 2,8.

Iris.ai og Yewno's metode til AI-drevet søgning har baggrund i teknikker såsom beregningssemantik, grafteori og maskinlæring (Hoepfner, 2018). Resultaterne af tænke-højt-testene viser, at informationsspecialister påvirkes af deres baggrund inden for informationsvidenskab, hvor de i kuraterede databaser arbejder med bloksøgninger, thesauri og dokumentrepræsentationer. Det er meget tydeligt, at testsystemerne præsenterer en helt ny måde at arbejde med informationssøgning og litteratur reviews. Vores testpersoner syntes, det var interessant at dykke ned i disse systemer, men det frustrerede testpersonerne, at de ikke kunne forstå, hvad der foregik "bag scenen" og i "maskinrummet". Forståelsen af systemarkitekturen er et meget vigtigt aspekt for informationsspecialister i forhold til undervisning, support, og at kunne yde professionel søgning- og forskningsstøtte af høj kvalitet. Både Iris.ai og Yewno konfronterede vores testpersoners faglige kompetence og udfordrede måden at søge og være systematisk på. Dette er en øjenåbner for brugen af AI-systemer i en bibliotekskontekst, der kræver nye fagligheder og definitioner af hvad en akademisk søgning *kan være*. Dette er noget vi bør være meget opmærksomme på.

I denne midtvejsrapport kunne vi ikke analysere, hvorvidt målene for hvordan akademisk søgning understøttes af AI systemerne og hvordan disse systemer kan skabe værdi for henholdsvis brugere og informationsfolk er nået. Der vil blive foretaget yderligere tests af flere forskellige brugertyper (forskere og studerende) i efteråret, så vi på baggrund af de allerede foretagne tænke-højt test i denne rapport, samt de forestående tests, kan vurdere effektiviteten og merværdien af de to systemer. Det er væsentligt at undersøge kvaliteten af de kilder systemerne søger i samt den akademiske kvalitet af de fremfundne dokumenter set fra brugerens perspektiv. Yderligere tests vil også omfatte brugernes faglige bedømmelse af relevans, om dokumentation og eksportmulighederne i systemerne opfylder deres forventninger til videnskabelige arbejde, metodologiske transparens og systemernes stabilitet.

Med denne samlede indsigt i informationsspecialisters og brugernes (forskere/studerende) professionelle adfærd i skabelsen af videnskabelige produkter ved brug af AI-systemer, foreligger der os en samlet vurdering som vi kan inddrage i anbefalinger for implementering af AI-søgesystemer og support i KB infrastruktur og sammenhængen med nuværende services.

1. Introduction

This report assesses the performance of two AI-powered search systems identified in Delivery 1: identification of AI-software (10.5281/zenodo.4279008). The tested systems are Iris.ai and Yewno. The systems are described in detail in the report. Tests were conducted in Iris.ai in week 17, April 2021 and in Yewno in weeks 24 and 25, June 2021. Think-aloud tests with information specialists were used to explore the extent the functionalities in the two systems support academic search methods and actions. An academic search is understood as a search method where transparency, reproducibility, documentation and reliability are key. At the same time the think-aloud tests will challenge the information specialists, and get them to formulate their insights in the efficiency of the systems and the needs for AI-enhanced support at the library.

The report summarizes think-aloud tests in the two systems, particularly the extent the systems support academic searching with a view to support effective and transparent literature search. The report will inform decisions in further tests of the systems where researchers and students will be included and ultimately whether subscription and ambitions with the two systems will be renewed, amended or cancelled, the type and form of system support that needs to be implemented or if further testing and comparison with other software is advised. Support through searching using AI-powered technologies can be provided in a multitude of ways – through saving time, through searching more efficiently and effectively, through providing new avenues of discovery and through transparency and documentation. We have a working hypothesis in the project that different types of users (student, senior researchers and library staff) place different values on different types of support.

The report works with the following objectives and research questions. In this mid-term report we cannot analyse whether the objectives have been met, further tests including users (researchers and students) will be held in the Autumn to enable us to assess the efficiency, added-value, the scope for implementation and coherence.

1.1 Overall project objectives and research questions

Objectives

- Identify AI-powered search systems that supports efficient and relevant outcomes for academic searchers
- Identify AI-powered search systems that improve discovery in our own collections
- Identify AI-powered search systems that supplement the current service portfolio at the Royal Library, Denmark
- Ensure the usefulness of the AI-powered search system for diverse user groups (information specialists, students, Ph.D., researchers and other disciplines)
- Argue for the placement of the AI-powered search system in the KB infrastructure “Biblioteksservice & Partnerskaber” (KUB, Rub, AUL) [*Library Service and Partnerships, Copenhagen University Library, Roskilde University Library and Aarhus University Library*], Afdelingen for Bibliotekssystem [*The Department of Library Systems*], Afdeling for Licensforvaltning [*Department of License Negotiation*] and KB Digital [*Department of Digitalisation at the Royal Library, Denmark*].
- Present for library managers what a resulting AI-search service at the library could look like

Research Questions

- How do the AI-powered search systems Iris.ai and Yewno Discover support an academic search, where values such as the efficiency, trustworthiness, quality, reliability, documentation and transparency of a system are paramount?

- Which value does Iris.ai and Yewno add to the academic search process for users?
- Which value does Iris.ai and Yewno add to the academic search process for information professionals?

2. Method

Think-aloud tests were designed to test the extent an academic search could be conducted in the two AI-powered search systems, Iris.ai (<https://Iris.ai/>) and Yewno Discover (<https://www.yewno.com/discover>). Pilot tests and validation tests were undertaken with two independent reviewers in March 2021. The validity tests were based on the principles outlined in Kim (2009), testing the content, face and construct validity of the test instrument (appendix 1). Consequently, the grammar and consistency of the language were improved and questions were reframed before the final think-aloud tests were conducted in April-June 2021 (Appendix 2).

Ten information specialists were invited to take part in the tests. One test person from the Yewno tests dropped out of the study, resulting in an overall drop-out rate of 10%. Accordingly, five think-aloud tests in Iris.ai and four in Yewno were held at the university libraries in Aarhus and Copenhagen.

The demographics of the remaining nine test persons are found in table 1 and 2:

Table 1: demographics of test persons (Iris.ai)

Gender	Specialty	Experience SR*	Experience Iris.ai
Male	Social Sciences, Psychology, teaching SR and search techniques.	Intermediate	Beginner
Female	Social Sciences, Psychology, teaching SR	Good	Beginner
Male	Technical Sciences,	Expert	Beginner
Female	Technical Sciences, Licenses at KB,	Intermediate	Beginner
Female	Social Sciences, Law	Expert	Beginner

Table 2: demographics of test persons (YEWNO)

Gender	Specialty	Experience SR*	Experience Yewno
Female	Humanities, UX, Researcher Support, Study Environment	Intermediate	Beginner
Female	Teaching SR, contact librarian, Humanities, Social Sciences and Technology	Expert	Beginner
Female	Social Sciences, Anthropology, Sociology, teaching SR and search methods	Expert	Beginner
Male	Teaching search and SR methods, History, Pedagogy & didactics	Expert	Beginner

*SR = systematic search and review

Two testers ran each test. One, as the moderator, conducted the dialogue and guided the test person through the tasks set in the think-aloud test. The second, noted down the test persons behavior, humour and comments. All tests were recorded using Zoom, both audio, and screen were recorded as well as the test persons behaviour was observed. The recordings were saved to Edumedia for the duration of the project and destroyed thereafter.

The tests began with a set of pre-test questions, inquiring into the test persons knowledge and expertise in information seeking, likewise the extent of their expertise in searching using AI-powered technology. Each test person searched the AI-powered search system using the same case. The case was presented to the test person at the start of the think-aloud test. No preparation or prior knowledge of the case was required. Each test person completed a series of tasks to test the functionality of the system, the transparency of the search and their own understanding of the search process in each system. After the test was complete, each test person answered a set of questions designed to make them reflect over the search and rate their satisfaction with the system.

3. Test systems

3.1 Iris.ai, <https://Iris.ai/>

Iris.ai navigates Open Access literature, primarily in the disciplines of health and chemistry, but also in other sources that can be tailored to fit the users' needs. Topic modelling and "finger printing" technology is used to display results to the user in topic maps, which the user can then filter their way through to increase specificity. Iris.ai offers free and paid versions of the product, that allow to varying degrees, according to negotiation with the vendor, integration with organizational and subscription databases, collaboration and multi-user functionalities, relevance filters, bookmarking, the possibility to establish inclusion and exclusion criteria to the search, import functions and RSS feeds.

Iris.ai can export to CSV and Excel and has a very engaging graphical interface that makes the created knowledge map clear and interactive.

Demands to the users technical understanding of the programme and supported algorithms are low (<https://Iris.ai/>)

To be able to make valuable searches in Iris.ai, it is important to view and use Iris.ai as a discovery tool and not a tool to be used as a traditional database. In a traditional database systematic search is an effective method to search within specific fields. In Iris.ai an efficient and effective search is done in a different way. The searching is not straightforward for users and how to get started with Iris.ai need some attention or teaching to master.

Main features of Iris.ai and terminology

Analysis monitor – In the focus tool the Analysis Monitor indicates which stage you are currently in, and a slide –bar shows number of papers included or excluded, based on your choice of concepts and topics in the different stages. This viewing does not include papers you manually decided to include or exclude. The Analysis Monitor also shows the efficiency of the system contra manual screening and it shows precision/recall.

Bookmarking – Save a map by clicking on the "bookmark" icon.

Concepts - "A concept is one word representing an idea that can be found in the papers loaded in the Focus tool. Iris.ai has a conceptual understanding of the word and its contextual synonyms. Adding concepts for inclusion/exclusion will not only include/exclude papers with that exact keyword in it, but also papers using contextually similar words." (Verified 04-08-2021: <https://help.Iris.ai/focus-tool/focus-overall-directions/>)

Exploring tool - A search starts with the exploring tool by typing in 300-500 words into the statement box. Typically, this is an abstract copied from a core publication or an URL to an open access publication. Iris.ai

describes the exploring as: “It is built this way by design, in order to increase the chances of serendipity and that you just might come across a new idea, a different way of thinking, or a rabbit hole to jump on for inspiration.” (Verified 04-08-2021: <https://help.Iris.ai/explore-tool/explore-overall-directions/>)

Hide verified papers – This feature hides papers already manually included or excluded

Focus tool – Papers from the bookmarked maps in the exploring tool are transferred to the focus tool which comprise of three stages

Focus tool: stage one – in this stage you include or exclude papers based on specific user-defined concepts or concepts suggested by the system. Including concepts will overrule excluding concepts.

Focus tool: stage two – in this stage you include/exclude papers based on Global, Specific or Current topics. Global topics are very broad. Specific Topics are derived from all documents in the study and current topics are generated from the articles included in stage 1. Included topics both override excluded topics and excluded concepts in stage 1.

Focus tool: stage three – in this stage you refine the included papers manually by relevance and the result is exported.

Topics - A topic is a string of words representing a group of documents. Iris.ai is asked to group the papers loaded into the tool - where one paper can be part of multiple groups. When Iris.ai is asked to describe each group, it does so with a string of 10 words that have to be read together, and cannot be altered. A topic is therefore associated with a specific and numbered group of papers, and when a topic is included/excluded, that exact group of papers is the one included/excluded. (Verified 04-08-2021: <https://help.Iris.ai/focus-tool/focus-overall-directions/>)

Visual map (knowledge map) - is generated based on the text entered in the statement box in the exploring tool. The map consists of the concepts found in the input text and their relationship to each other. Each cell of the map references to found articles. Maps can be edited by deleting concepts and filtering by year and database.

3.2 Yewno Discover: <https://www.yewno.com/>

Yewno Discover (Yewno) is a multidisciplinary tool that enables the user to search using ideas and concepts rather than keywords. It is designed as a way to develop questions in research projects and get the user to think about the vocabulary they use to frame their work. Technically, this means that full-text analysis is conducted through the use of computational semantics, neural networks, & Machine-Learning. In a graphic display of results in a concept map, important nodes of concepts are differentiated from ideas related to the concept. The maps are presented in defined contexts, and change according to the context the user finds most useful. Relevance of the retrieved documents is aided through the “snippets” function. Snippets show the strongest piece(s) of text in the document related to the concepts or relationships. Access to the literature is gained by clicking on the nodes on the map. The aim is to learn from resources that might have otherwise been overlooked and enhance understanding, but also save time while “ensuring comprehensive and credible coverage” [source citation: <https://www.yewno.com/discover>]. Yewno can be integrated with the library’s other library systems, and can search in academic or government documents published in English, German or Chinese.

Main features of Yewno Discover and terminology

Concepts – In Yewno the search starts by typing a search term in the query box. Yewno then uses full-text to derive concepts and their definitions. The result is a list of concepts. The user navigates across concepts and relationships between concepts. Yewno uses a concept search to identify semantic connections and conceptual links from between articles, books, and databases. Yewno does not do known item searching.

Document – Each concept or relationship has a corresponding documents tab. The documents listed are ordered with the strongest semantic connections at the top.

Knowledge Map – a knowledge map is generated after a search is performed. It provides a visual representation of the relationship between concepts. Hovering over the nodes activates connections between concepts.

Node – A node is a circle on the Knowledge Map. Each node represents a concept. Larger nodes are the "primary concepts" and smaller nodes are the "secondary concepts."

Notes – The user can take notes by using the function "create note"

Relationship – Relationships are illustrated as lines connecting the nodes. Up to 8 concepts at a time can be used to generate relationships using the "multi-select" function. Relationships between nodes can be explored using the "layers" function.

Research Journey – The research journey is a record of the search, concepts that have been used, documents viewed and saved, and snapshots of knowledge maps. The Research Journey can be saved and steps on the journey exported. Snap shots of knowledge maps, snippets and concepts to Google Docs, and bibliographic information as a RIS file or as a CSV.

Slide Bar - The slide bar increases or decreases the number of concepts that display on a knowledge map. By grabbing the slider range in the middle and moving it up and down the user can also select the extent obvious or non-obvious are shown. Concepts shown at the bottom of the slide range have weaker semantic strength, which indicates that there are fewer scholarly publications containing those concepts in Yewno.

Snapshots – snapshots are a way to capture (take a screen shot of) a knowledge map and adding it the Research Journey.

Snippets - Shows the strongest piece of text in the document related to your concepts or relationships.

4. Results

In the following results of the think-aloud test for respectively Iris.ai and Yewno are presented. The results section is followed by a brief discussion of the two systems and the conclusions so far which will inform our next steps.

4.1 Iris.ai: Results of the think-aloud tests

4.1.1 Test persons overall experience of Iris.ai

The test persons liked the design of the system. They were disappointed in the lack of functionality of the system to assist in sorting, filtering and evaluating the relevance of the found material. This made the test persons suspicious of the quality of Iris.ai and they thought they had to put “too much” effort into getting to know the system.

Some of the test persons commented that Iris.ai requires knowledge of a field/domain and therefore is more suited for researchers rather than for students. On the contrary, others suggested that Iris.ai could be useful for bachelor or master students. Although most test persons did not think that Iris.ai supported a systematic search, they found it useful for the explorative phase of the search and once mastery in Iris.ai is achieved, a useful supplement to other databases. The test persons saw the value of Iris.ai increase if it is developed further.

The test persons were asked to rate their satisfaction with the exploring tool, the focus tool and Iris.ai as an overall tool. The overall satisfaction of Iris.ai was given from a point of view where some test persons considered themselves to be on “unknown territory”. The Exploring tool and Focus tool were assessed separately as they are the main features of Iris.ai. Both tools present a result based on semantic and conceptual similarity to the user input rather than focusing on specific keywords and therefore give the user a more conceptual understanding of the topic

The ratings were on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is very unsatisfied, 2 not satisfied, 3 neutral, 4 satisfied and 5 is very satisfied. The Exploring tool scored a mean satisfaction of 2.6, Focusing tool score 3 and the overall satisfaction score for Iris.ai was 2.8. All in all, the test persons rated the system as below satisfactory (see table below).

Satisfaction scores on three parameters in Iris.ai

	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	mean (range)
Exploring tool	4	2	3	1	3	2.6 (1-4)
Focus tool	4	3	3	2	3	3 (2-4)
Iris.ai overall	3	3	4	1	3	2.8 (1-4)

The low satisfaction scores were mostly attributed to the lack of transparency of the search, the non-intuitiveness or their lack of comprehension of the Exploring tool, and the different concepts and topic in Focus tool and how these were selected by the algorithm. The test persons were slightly more positive about the Focus tool. They indicated that the low score was due to not knowing the system and topic to the necessary degree.

4.1.2 Efficiency of search

At the end of each think-aloud test, test persons were asked to consider the efficiency of Iris.ai.

When it comes to the efficiency of Iris.ai the information specialists did not reach an agreement. Some could see a very good efficiency in the “find related papers” search method where Iris.ai presented results based on a primary source (a research paper central for the problem statement). Others were very critical

about the relatively small search result (102 references) and were not impressed by the efficiency at all. One stated Iris.ai might have value at the beginning of a search – and could be an efficient tool to gain an overview of a topic area.

None of the test persons understood the percentages in the “Analysis monitor” – if the idea of the analysis monitor is to show some sort of efficiency, it was misunderstood by the test persons and caused confusion.

The majority of the test persons expressed that the efficiency in the test situation probably was affected by their lack of knowledge of the system and the case.

4.1.3 Transparency and reliability

The transparency of how the search was conducted in the system and how the results were reached was evaluated at the end of each think-aloud test. The overall experience of the test persons was that there was very little transparency and that it felt like searching in a “black box”, not knowing what was inside and how the search was implemented. It was unclear where the concepts and topics came from and how the choice of concepts - and especially topics - affected the result. One test person thought the search was the opposite of systematic and that control was lost. One person commented that working with concepts was a waste of time when the result included topics that pulled papers containing excluded concepts back into the results.

All test persons wondered why they got fewer papers in the focusing tool when importing a bookmarked map from the exploring tool. It was also unclear to some of the test persons which databases they were searching in and if the content had been through some kind of quality control.

The majority felt that trust in the result required expert knowledge of both the subject and Iris.ai. Further, attaining proficiency in Iris.ai would be very time consuming.

4.1.4 Quality of search

The test setup did not include evaluation of the academic or methodological quality of the retrieved papers.

4.1.5 Documentation

Good documentation is a prerequisite of a systematic search method and likewise responsible conduct of research. To document information seeking, common practice is to use reference managers (e.g. Endnote, Zotero) and export the references from the database and save them locally. Along with the references a “search protocol” or “search history” are tools to document when, where and which search string were implemented in the database. The test persons were asked to reflect on the ability to document their work in Iris.ai. All test persons struggled to save their work and were in doubt if saving was even possible. Only some were satisfied with the documentation in regard to their search. They liked that they, in their profile in Iris.ai, could go back and view bookmarked maps and choice of included/excluded concepts and topic but they would have liked to be able to export the choices for reproducibility. All test persons found it disappointing that they could not export their search-result and references direct to other reference managers than Zotero. They were however satisfied with the possibilities in Iris.ai to export to CSV and Excel. However, the export was not intuitive for the test persons and therefore it failed for some of them. The data in the exported files were satisfying, but some wished that Iris.ai would export the content from the topics also – this was not the case.

Full reporting of the search method helps the reader to assess the strength and comprehensiveness of the search and makes it easier to update and expand on the original search as new evidence is published. With no clear search string, but rather a problem statement, followed by a series of choices to include or exclude concepts and topics, reproducibility is impossible. This aspect left some of the test persons with a mistrust of their own professional competencies when it came to choose concepts in Iris.ai.

4.1.6 Support systematic search

When searching systematically it is important to know how the search is conducted, how the choices affect the result and be able to document the search for reproducibility. Iris.ai was not considered by any of the test persons to support a systematic approach to searching. One test person described it as “losing control”. One could see the advantage of Iris.ai searching faster than usual across multiple databases, but still the control was lost. One test person said that it was possible to use Iris.ai systematically but that it would require a lot of time and effort to know exactly how Iris.ai works. Instead of supporting a systematic search, a couple of the test persons found Iris.ai to be better in the explorative phase, getting to know the subject before conducting systematic searching in other databases.

4.1.7 Support discovery

Some test persons found that Iris.ai supports discovery and suggest Iris.ai could be used either by researchers/students in the explorative phase of the search or as a supplement to other databases on par with citation databases. When relevant papers are found in other databases, they can be gathered in Iris.ai and related papers identified. Iris.ai was also considered a valuable tool for the information specialist to explore a topic before meeting with the researcher.

4.1.8 Relevance

The test persons had difficulty assessing the relevance of the search results, as the case used in the think-aloud test was not their area of expertise. Therefore, the test persons expressed that their lack of knowledge of the field (Fear of childbirth in expectant fathers) affected their ability to assess the relevance of the retrieved results. All test persons did however identify some relevant articles that they would recommend to a user.

Quality of the search result can be difficult to measure, since our test persons were information specialists and not specifically engaged in the research subject in the test. Likewise, the test persons found it difficult to judge the relevance of the articles, because of their lack of knowledge in the field. This made some of the tasks in the think-aloud test more random for some test persons. The test persons felt that they did not have the necessary competencies to judge what to include or exclude in a proper way.

4.1.9 User-friendliness

In regard to user-friendliness our test persons reported both pros and cons.

Iris.ai was launched in September 2016 (verified 05-08-2021: <https://help.Iris.ai/basics-of-the-Iris.ai-ai-science-assistant/proven-tools/>) and has been continuously developed since then. The setup and design are engaging, especially the graphic map/knowledge map in the Explore tool was pointed out by one test person as something nice and clear and something that “looked good” One test person had however, a small objection to the graphic interface: It was difficult to hit exact years on the “slider” when filtering out on range of year. The conclusion from the test persons: looks good, but can be difficult to handle.

Further, the test persons liked the “hide verified papers” options in Stage two of the Focus tool and missed this functionality in Stage three. They would have liked other filter options in Stage two and three, such as databases and also the ability to add some of the filters from the graphic map later on in the search process (e.g. year). One test person commented that references should have had unique identification numbers and that numbers would have made the overview better.

There was general confusion about the terminology of the Iris.ai system and how to find concepts. The system only showed the first 30 concepts in alphabetical order. However, some test persons, because of their lack of knowledge of the search case, were very satisfied that Iris.ai suggested concepts to consider. The excluded/included slide-bar on the results page (Focus tool stages one, two and three) frustrated the test persons. Some didn’t see it and therefore didn’t understand the result. Others were confused that it only contained papers automatically in- and excluded by the system and not the papers they had excluded themselves. All our test persons were information specialists and very set in the world of Boolean logic. That made the exclude/include options in Iris.ai. confusing. One test person felt that it was more important to know what she didn’t want than what she wanted and that is a very different way of thinking.

It was not intuitive how to save the work in the different stages and the export to CSV was difficult for many. Some were also doubting whether they could “go back” to previous stages, and if so, how to retrace their steps.

During some of the tests, Iris.ai had technical issues. When creating the map in the Exploring tool it froze and, in the end, an error message was displayed. However, After a couple of attempts, the issues disappeared and the test could continue.

4.2 Yewno: Results of the think-aloud tests

4.2.1 Test persons overall experience of Yewno

All test persons described Yewno as a discovery tool and compared it to a reference work or subject dictionary. The main functionality of Yewno was seen as a place to explore a topic rather than a tool that supports academic literature search. Even though Yewno was not considered to support a systematic approach to searching, the test persons pointed out that Yewno could play a supplementary role in the academic literature search process. All test persons agreed that Yewno would be useful at project start to discover more about a research problem, examine concepts, get an overview of the interrelations in and possible directions of a research area, and through serendipity discover new and unexpected concepts and relations.

The test persons were asked to rate their satisfaction with knowledge maps, snippets and Yewno as an overall tool. The ratings were on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is very unsatisfied, 2 not satisfied, 3 neutral, 4 satisfied and 5 is very satisfied, Table 3. Knowledge maps and snippets were specifically isolated for assessment as they are the end-product of Yewno’s processing of its corpus of literature, a process that uses a deep learning network to extract and group topics, allowing searchers to explore a complex network of interrelated literature. The result presented to the user in the form of knowledge maps and snippets is based on the query’s meaning rather than specific keywords and thus helps the user

understand the semantic meaning of the conceptual units, build associations between different disciplines, discover literature across domains and scanning the language in these related snippets quickly gives the user a concept overview of the local knowledge domain. Knowledge maps scored a mean satisfaction score of 3.75, snippets 2.25 and the overall satisfaction score for Yewno was 3.

Table 3. Satisfaction scores on three parameters in Yewno

	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	mean (range)
Knowledge maps	3	3	5	4	3.75 (3-5)
Snippets	3	2	1	3	2.25 (1-3)
Yewno overall	1	4	3	3	2.75 (1-4)

The rating was on a scale of 1 to 5, where scores 4 and over indicated satisfaction with the system. The test persons rated the system as below satisfactory. Satisfaction scores were also reduced by the lack of transparency of the search, the lack of specificity in the concepts and the design of the Yewno interface. Transparency and specificity are presented in the next section. Regarding interface design, the icons used in Yewno to depict functionalities were considered too small, the pop-up messages from the system to the user disappeared too quickly and the difference in colour between active and inactive nodes on a knowledge map was too subtle. Further, one of our test persons who was colour blind, could not see the change in colour at all.

4.2.2 Efficiency of search

Efficiency was evaluated at the end of each think-aloud test. Each test comprised of multiple searches, and in the test setup we considered it more meaningful to evaluate the efficiency of Yewno as a whole rather than evaluate the efficiency of each concept query or the performance of each individual function. Queries and actions within the session were not independent of one another, and the test persons were quick to adapt their behavior throughout the test. The test persons learned from interacting with Yewno and began to expect the production of lists of concepts and knowledge maps. Their behaviour and comments indicated that they needed more specific concepts, in the form of a concept hierarchy or thesaurus and the option to combine multiple concepts from the very start of the search. Having to identify one concept at a time and find the “best fit” was not considered an efficient approach to searching.

The test setup restricted the test person’s time to explore the linked structure of the knowledge maps in depth to support learning more about the topic. Learning is a part of search behaviour that in normal conditions the test persons stated they would prefer to use a lot of time on, chiefly to reflect over the relevance of the concepts and improve understanding of the search topic and query. Yewno optimizes the efficiency of the learning experience through providing the searcher with text snippets taken from retrieved documents to aid in evaluation of relevance, estimated reading times of retrieved documents and knowledge maps instead of lists of ranked references to get an efficient overview of a research topic, find relevant papers, and identify important concepts. These components operate at different levels of the search, determining how content is retrieved, ranked, organized, and presented. However, the test persons had difficulty understanding how these components contributed to query understanding and presentation of results.

4.2.3 Transparency and reliability

The test persons were asked to assess the transparency of the search and agreed, taken at face value, Yewno search was transparent. They chose a concept and this concept was displayed in a map in the context of related concepts. It was first when the test persons started to critically investigate the prevalence of the searched concept in the retrieved papers that they started to doubt the transparency and reliability of the system. As discussed further in section 4.2.8, it was not clear if and how the searched concept was weighted in the text snippets or if synonyms were used instead. When two or more concepts were searched, the test persons were unsure if all concepts were included in the retrieved papers (equated to Boolean “AND”) or just one of the concepts (equated to Boolean “OR”). The test persons also noted that some of the retrieved documents were missing bibliographic metadata that could be used to verify the work, and one considered lack of verification a factor which further reduced the transparency of the search. They were not able to document their chosen selection criteria, did not understand why the research journey was not interactive (section 4.2.5) and commented that searching in Yewno returned so many results that a “Google effect” would affect their selection of relevant documents – they would only look through the first few pages of results.

4.2.4 Quality of search

The test setup did not include evaluation of the academic or methodological quality of the retrieved papers. However, test persons noted that a large extent of retrieved papers were old and unacademic.

4.2.5 Documentation

Yewno documents actions taken in the system in the research journey, where concepts that have been used, documents viewed and saved, and snapshots of knowledge maps are recorded and steps in this journey exported to Google Docs, and bibliographic information as a RIS file or as a CSV. The test persons were disappointed to discover that the journey steps in Yewno were not interactive, thus they could not return to a previous map or step in the search process. No historical documentation of search tactics was provided. The test persons were asked to export the journey steps (saved maps and concepts). Export to Google Docs was easy, however chronology was lost as all maps were presented together and then all concepts in the Google Doc. This lack of systematic documentation was seen as a hindrance to the efficiency of the system. The Yewno interface invites to discovery to the extent that as the test persons linked from concept to concept, they got distracted and lost focus of the search case and became disoriented in the system. All test persons expressed difficulty in getting back on track with the search, and being able to return to their original query. They missed a traditional search history that could be used to re-run and replicate a search.

The test persons were also asked to export bibliographic information of the retrieved documents. They exported to both CSV and RIS and found the quality of the bibliographic acceptable. Important information to identify each document was included in the export. Yewno also offers a notebook in which to record thoughts and ideas throughout the search, however none of the test persons could get the notebook function to work. Some could not write in the notebook, while others could not save their notes.

4.2.6 Support systematic search

Yewno was not considered by the test persons to support a systematic approach to searching. Yewno is designed to visualise a search and make navigating the search more accessible to the novice user³. It does not do known item searching, but rather suggests potential directions and ways to explore a topic.

4.2.7 Support discovery

The test persons agreed that the strength of Yewno is its ability to support discovery. Yewno adds an additional discovery layer on top of full text items in the corpus by reaching down into the texts themselves to identify concepts in the context of multiple topics. The visual presentation of concepts as interactive maps that link to related concepts and literature was successful. However, the applicability of the concepts, maps and linked literature in practice was found to limit the control of the search and be frustrating by the test persons. First, only one concept at a time can be written in the query box and then only after a suitable concept was retrieved by the system could a second concept be searched and added to knowledge map. Second, the test persons were unsure if clicking on the relationship line linking two nodes resulted in documents that contain both nodes or either node. Third, the frequency and placement of concepts in the retrieved snippets was not highlighted. The majority of the test persons noted that the concepts did not appear in the snippets at all.

Using the multi-select function, the test persons were able to investigate the interrelations of up to eight concepts. This function was seen as an exciting and broad approach to the search and a great aid in helping the user discover the landscape of a topic. The function did not work first time for all the test persons. Everyone struggled with isolating a concept-node and choosing it using the multi-select tool, one person could not select the concepts they wanted to include and chose to include random concepts to complete the task, the system crashed in two cases, was slow in all cases causing two participants to click “refresh” and consequently lose their previous work and journey steps. On the second or third try the multi-select function worked for all of the test persons. Finally, the test persons were disappointed that new concepts could not be added to a map created using the multi-select function. A resulting map, built on eight concepts is densely populated with concepts and relationships. Hovering the mouse over the map activates all the relationships and the node labels are covered in relationship lines which was a cause of frustration. However, the maps also engaged the test persons in the positive experience of questioning the links between concepts, exploring new terminology and motivating them to explore.

“Layers” is an advanced function of Yewno that allows the user to explore indirect relationships between selected concepts from a map. When a layer has been generated, the user cannot add new concepts to the layer however they can link to related literature. Layers must be created from the original knowledge map, the so called “top layer”. Layers provoked different reactions in our test persons. There was confusion if the layers were a search history for maps, questioning if the layers represented the different searches they had made during the test, (2 persons), or if there was a chronological hierarchy in the layers (3 persons). 1 person noted correctly that layers is similar to focusing the search to further explore the topic in a certain direction. As such not all maps are included in the layers. Layers are first created when the multi-select tool has been used. Maps generated from expanding concepts are not included in the layers. However, all test persons appreciated the idea of being able to go “travel” from one concept to another and create relationships that were linked to evidence in the literature. Yet, the different functionalities of the three maps (maps created by expanding concepts, maps created by multi-select and layers) was confusing as in appearance all the maps look identical.

4.2.8 Relevance

Test persons were asked to assess the relevance of the first 10 ranked documents, where retrieved documents were first ranked “by publication time” (newest first) and then “by relevance”. Relevance was assessed quickly in regards to the search case and was affected by each test persons knowledge and to some extent assumptions about the case and fictive project requirements. The test persons evaluated 0 – 5 documents out of 10 relevant when ranking by publication date, and 0-8 relevant when ranking “by relevance”. It is worth noting that the same test person judged zero relevant in both rankings and chose only to include dissertations, whereas the remaining test persons included articles, books and book

chapters. Also worth noting, and commented on by the test persons, was the age of the ranked documents. When ranking by relevance, documents in the top ten were published between 1990 and 2015 (dissertations 2012-2019) and when ranking by publication time recent documents from 2021 topped the list.

For both rankings, by publication time and by relevance, the test persons noted that none of the documents were “spot on” but were worth looking at for further information and inspiration.

Yewno does not display how many documents were retrieved in total, but displays the amount of document snippets retrieved. Snippets are the strongest piece(s) of text in the document related to the searched concepts or relationships. Thus, one document may contain many snippets. Snippets did not meet the requirements of the test persons. They expected to see snippets highlighted in the context of the retrieved document which Yewno does not do. Neither were the searched concepts highlighted in the snippet. Two test persons used ctrl+f to find the concepts in the snippet, and another commented that snippets appeared to be random, referring to “discussion theme four” or the title of a table in the main document.

4.2.9 User friendliness

The test persons commented that Yewno provides a simple and intuitive way to search, encouraging them to explore the connections between concepts and the related literature seamlessly. On the other hand, this ease of search also distracted the test persons from the transparency of the search method and the quality of the resources being searched in or why the search retrieves a particular set of papers. The test persons were quick to learn how to search, navigate, and interact with the Yewno interface. The interface is not overly complex however the icons are small and colour changes indicating an action has been taken are too subtle. The interface is well organized with the actions the user has taken on the left, maps in the center and analysis functionalities on the right. The system is missing clear communication with the user when it is creating maps, particularly when using multi-select. The test persons were unsure if the system had timed out, was working or crashed. The test persons discovered with disappointment that only two concepts at a time could be identified as related. However, the intuitive approach of linking between concepts presented with their definitions and papers freed the test person from reading a lot of text to find and define core concepts and discover connections (or missing connections) in the literature that could inform a research project. Further, the system gives access to broad content quickly and in a smooth way. Integration with Google Docs worked seamlessly, thus supporting collaboration and documentation. The test persons raised concerns regarding the reliability of Yewno. All test persons experienced either the system crashing or functions not working or both. Yewno did not consistently save searches (footsteps) after logging out. Yewno has been quick to respond to bugs, requests for fixes and suggested improvements.

5. Discussion

Learning about AI-systems for literature seeking and finding research papers has been a very interesting journey. The results of the think-aloud tests show that information specialists are affected by their background in the field of information science and it is very clear that the test systems present a whole new way of working with information seeking and literature reviews. Our test persons found it interesting to dive into those systems, but in the short timeframe of the tests failed to understand what’s going on “behind the scene” and in the “engine room”. Understanding the system architecture is very important for information specialists to facilitate teaching, scholarship, and provide professional research support of high

quality. Both Iris.ai and Yewno confronted our test persons' professional competence and challenged the way searching and being systematic is thought about. This is an eye-opener to the use of AI-systems in a library context and something we should be very aware of and work towards accommodating.

Iris.ai and Yewno's method of processing content is AI driven, applying computational semantics, graph theory, and machine learning to the full text of ingested documents (Hoepfner, 2018). Hoepfner explains that the AI reads the documents, infers meaning, learns and produces a neural network model creating inferences. Using full text instead of metadata is designed to avoid problems that can be caused by inconsistent metadata that can impact discoverability and relevancy ranking. Accordingly, in both Iris.ai and Yewno metadata quality does not affect the ability of the AI to process the paper nor the surfacing of a paper in the results and thus discovery is improved and more comprehensive.

5.1 Iris.ai, Yewno and the academic search

An academic search is defined in the AI-project as having the qualities of efficiency, quality, reliability, documentation and transparency. We recognise that the searcher has to critically evaluate the quality of the retrieved documents as they would in any search in any database. This aspect was not tested in the think-aloud tests. We do however expect that as a product design for education and research discovery, Iris.ai and Yewno presents a corpus of scholarly literature.

Test persons commented they could not search in the systematic, comprehensive and transparent way that they were trained to do and had limited control of the search process. While both Iris.ai and Yewno have a search query box, Boolean searching, fielded searches, known item, and in the case of Yewno even natural language searching are not supported. Instead, Iris.ai works by searching concepts identified in a problem statement and Yewno works best when users enter one concept to start exploring. Searching in Iris.ai require a longer text – an abstract – to even start searching. Between 300-500 words are required to start searching. The idea of Keywords is not existing. One person commented that the search could be biased when based on only one abstract. One test person was quick to accept that Yewno supports an "explorative study string" [in Danish: *Undersøgelsesstreng*] instead of a search string. This statement can be applied to Iris.ai as well. For non-information professionals using Boolean and proximity operators, field tags and thesaurus terms correctly in search syntax can be complicated. AI-powered search provides concept-based discovery across multiple sources by using context to ensure relevance, reducing also the amount of time used on manual determination of relevance to the goal of the review which can bring a depth of discovery and speed to the review process which can have great value.

Iris.ai and Yewno do not have a thesaurus where broader and narrower terms, synonyms and related concepts are hierarchically organised in which the searcher can identify terms for their search. Concepts in both systems are created by extracting, processing, and linking to units of knowledge – concepts – from heterogeneous data sources, where similarity measures along different dimensions are used to group together related concepts. These concepts can be quite complex, but are presented to the user in a visually appealing way that invites even the novice searcher to explore. For the test persons, a lack of a thesaurus was both seen to encourage a more creative and intuitive approach to searching but also as a barrier to controlling the scope of the concepts and specificity of the search. One test person described searching in AI-powered systems as a paradigm shift in academic searching, much more user-friendly than a search building on thesaurus terms. Another described the search process as superficial, something immediately appealing and easy to understand, that would appeal to a very wide audience but has no substance as an academic tool.

The test persons appreciated the presentation of concepts in the format of a map in both systems. The map helped create an overview of terminology and a topical landscape. However, all agreed that the extent the concepts linked to useful documents was a concern and requires further investigation. The test persons were in doubt if they had found relevant literature, they missed being able to weight a concept (as in a block search, to increase the specificity of the search) and would have liked to be able to limit the search to peer-reviewed literature. Likewise, the extent to which the returned results contained the query concepts was disputed and the relevance ranking did not match the test persons determination of “real” relevance. In Yewno documents presented at the top of the search engine’s results page were judged the most relevant yet they appeared to be older papers, and this might lead to an outdated or incomplete view of the topic—especially when dealing with controversial or new issues.

As the main method of a literature study is the search, it is important for the transparency and integrity of the method to provide documentation that enables replication. A traditional search history is not provided in Iris.ai or Yewno. Traditionally a search history is chronological, each search string and applied filters are recorded in such a way that the search can be replicated, the history exported and automatically re-run in the database at a later date, as known from PubMed or Web of Science. Instead, Iris.ai has an excel sheet in which all references from the Focus tool are listed including bibliographic information, include and exclude labels, manual inclusion and stage. It is not an option to export a complete list of all included/excluded concepts and topics in text form. The topics are indeed listed for each reference but are displayed as coded unique identification numbers e.g. G46, not defining the terminology for each included topic. The maps created in the exploring stage are saved in the users profile. Yewno has a research journey that records automatically each concept searched and expanded in to a map, documents looked at and documents saved. Maps have to be saved manually through “snapshots.” Filters are not recorded. The test persons noted that they would have to write down in a separate document which concepts they searched and in which order, the amount of results each concept retrieved, which concepts were combined, the relationship between concepts, the number of retrieved results in total, filters applied and time and date of the search. The research journey documents used and expanded concepts, maps and documents, but the journey is not interactive. The user cannot return to a previous map and click in to concepts and documents or repeat earlier steps in the search. Export of the research journey or individual journey steps is easy. Export is supported to Google Docs, RIS files and CSV. The test persons tested all three export options. The export to Google Docs was seamless, however the export grouped all maps together, then concepts and then snippets with links to saved documents. Chronology and context were lost. For both Iris.ai and Yewno the ease of the RIS and CSV export was dependent on the test persons knowledge of how to work with these file formats. The completeness of the bibliographic information was as expected, some clean-up was needed regarding foreign characters and some bibliographic details had to be added.

In summary, Iris.ai and Yewno do not support what we traditionally understand as a systematic search but do encourage a comprehensive and cross-disciplinary search and forces the searcher to look at literature from domains in which they are only marginally familiar. Searches are documented on the level of recording which actions have been taken rather than detailing how these actions have been implemented in the system. It would be very difficult to replicate searches without substantial supplementary notes written throughout the search process.

5.2 Stepping away from the PubMed mindset of searching

Manual systematic literature reviews are becoming increasingly challenging due to the sharp rise in publications and cross disciplinary topics. AI-powered search offers tools that support the researcher in searching quickly and effectively and at the same time increasing the depth and breadth of the search.

Iris.ai searches a vast corpus of open access papers via Core¹ institutional repositories and includes the integration of PubMed² and Cordis³, which includes scientific papers, pre-prints and EU funded project reports. Yewno contains over 125 million English, German and Chinese scholarly documents. Scholarly does not necessarily mean peer-reviewed literature, as sources such as Wikipedia, newspapers and other sources of popular science are also included. Further, the corpora are not curated but are papers harvested from multiple sources. Searching using field tags, metadata and Boolean logic is not supported, instead machine learning enables the systems to model language in text form to get a more penetrating view of the literature rather than the exhaustive searches we know from traditional database. It would be a mistake therefore to compare an Iris.ai or Yewno search to a search in a curated and indexed platform such as Scopus or Web of Science. Particularly, the Yewno corpus can be to some extent compared to Google Scholar as it provides a broad search across many disciplines and sources: articles, theses, books, abstracts and court opinions, from academic publishers, professional societies, online repositories, universities and other websites. Which is why we recommend the AI-systems be used in conjunction with other tools. This approach we recognise from systematic search methodology - "Blindly using any research engine doesn't answer every question automatically." (Extance, 2018).

For many of our test persons (inclusive ourselves) there is an ingrained skepticism when hearing words like Artificial Intelligence, automation and efficiency. The idea of AI is enticing, but the practical and transparent systematic search that is so ingrained in librarians and information science professionals is challenged by the simplified approach to searching presented in AI-powered systems. Our test persons repeatedly stated that they could not use the search techniques that are part of a professional search in structured databases. AI-powered literature search includes different search technology. The technology has implications for the search methodology and the scope of the literature review, both in terms of lack of transparency and reproducibility but the search also brings deeper discovery and increased search speed across many different resources. Particular issues identified by our test persons are quality assessment of retrieved documents and the validity and reliability of the system, which have to be communicated to library users. Regarding the reliability of Iris.ai and Yewno, it appears that development of both systems will be continuing and adjustments for accuracy and relevance, will improve over time.

When preparing to perform academic and systematic searches, it is important to know the algorithm and understand the underlying information architecture in the database, to make sure you get the intended search result. When you are working systematically with your searches, you also have a thorough preparation that rarely opens up for serendipity. Serendipity refers to the finding of unexpected information while engaged in an information activity and the making of an intellectual leap of understanding with that information to arrive at an insight (Conrad and Moeller, 2017). In a systematic approach to searching all the choices made in the search are never wrong as long as they are rationalised, well-documented and transparent. When learning about Iris.ai we discovered that the system can find interdisciplinary connections and related concepts which you did not think about looking for yourself (the aspect of serendipity), and that might open new paths in a research project. Sometimes the results of the search in the AI-system do not make sense. Our test persons commented on what they considered was increased "noise" in the search results. Iris.ai describes it as: "*We rather want you to see noise - things that are not relevant - than to risk missing out of a piece of gold.*" (Verified 13-08-2021: <https://the.Iris.ai/faq>).

Conrad and Moeller (2017) found that searchers decide to follow recommendations from the search system based on a combination of perception of relevance to the field of study, access to the

¹ Core.ac.uk

² <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects/en>

recommended article, and trust in the provider. More about trust in the following section. Serendipity in discovery is considered to be important as it plays a key role in the way people seek information. Users of discovery tools work differently from users in databases that support traditional systematic searches (known item searches). They re-frame their information needs as they search based on the information they encounter. Resembles a hermeneutic approach to searching, that is particularly useful in systematic reviews in the Humanities (Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2010) and already an established methodology that can be systematized. Many useful information discoveries are unintentional and searchers enjoy this serendipitous discovery. Both Conrad (2017) and Boell (2010) argue that serendipitous discovery bolsters user engagement and creates user satisfaction. Iris.ai and Yewno foster serendipity in their content. However, documenting the search is difficult, as it is hard to define. As we experienced in our think-aloud tests, it requires more of the searcher to manually note their thoughts and actions continuously. We also experienced that Iris.ai and Yewno engaged our test persons. They were quick to accept Iris.ai and Yewno as a new way of searching and enjoyed the freedom of discovery. AI-powered search indicates a culture change in the approach to an academic search and expectations to recall and precision in search system. Our test group comprised of searchers new to Iris.ai and Yewno and also AI-powered searching as a whole. With more practice our test group would undoubtedly become more proficient in searching in discovery systems and stop comparing their search experience in these systems with experience in curated and structured databases and start implementing other standards to document search methods and develop best practices for documentation.

5.3 Trust in AI system

Accordingly, a systematic approach to the search in Iris.ai and Yewno cannot be documented with the same level of transparency as we expect to see in a systematic search conducted in curated databases. Yet we must be aware that search standards are also evolving to encompass a more inclusive approach to searching. Look at the latest update of the PRISMA statement for example where items have been modified to facilitate advances in methods to identify, select, appraise, and synthesise studies, particularly “technological advances have enabled the use of natural language processing and machine learning to identify relevant evidence” (Page et al. 2021, p.1). However, to rethink requirements to a search and defend the methodology in supervision with students and researchers, trust in the system is paramount. The information specialist requires not only current knowledge of developments in search standards but also increased knowledge of system architecture and how implemented algorithms effect recall, precision, specificity and sensitivity of the search. If users do not trust the technology, they are not going to use it (Hancock et al., 2011). However, performance, referring to a reliable, robust product, is not the only dimension that influences trust. In a report from 2019, Tschopp (2020) concluded that firstly, users can be sceptical about an AI-system but still find the right level of trust to use the technology properly without becoming overly reliant on the system. Secondly, the technology providers must earn user trust through demonstrating trustworthiness. We are particularly impressed with the openness of both Iris.ai and Yewno to our requests for development of functionalities and speed in which bugs have been solved.

5.4 Strengths and weaknesses of Iris.ai and Yewno

Table 2: Strengths and weakness of Iris.ai and Yewno

System	Strengths	Weaknesses
Iris.ai	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggest related concepts • Search faster in more articles • Metadata quality does not effect retrieval • Can show new relations between subjects • Visual Knowledge map • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to understand how the algorithms in the systems are and to understand how to use the system • Require time to get to know the tool • Not easy to master • Not strong in searching in e.g., Danish language • Limited documentation of strategy
Yewno	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggest related concepts • Unexpected links between topics • Links direct to literature • Intuitive/Easy to use • Generate idea/hypothesis • Metadata quality does not effect retrieval • Multidisciplinary • Seamless links to full-text 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not mature/Bugs • Limited documentation • Small font size • Subtle colour choices • Hover over function on map • Not transparent search • Not reproducible method • Limited to English, Chinese and German text

The graphical presentation of the knowledge map in Iris.ai was considered by the test persons as “nice”. The map gives an overview when searching and makes it possible to see new connections between subjects. This is a new way of showing search results. Using the map effectively requires expert knowledge of the search case. Only with knowledge of the subject can the user edit the map critically and choose the right concepts that define the research question and purpose of the overall project correctly. The algorithm retrieves relevant aspects but it also shows something completely irrelevant which both inspires discovery but also creates frustration and noise. Here the knowledge and professionalism of the user needs to be applied so correct concepts and words can be included, not relevant concepts and terms excluded and the search run again. When editing the knowledge map in the Exploring tool it is important not to exclude too many concepts because it narrows down the search result too early in the process. In the Focus tool, however, it is important to *exclude* uninteresting concepts rather than *include* too many or too broad concepts or topics because the included concepts and topics overrule the excluded ones. This can result in confusion and a feeling that the work done in Stage 1 is wasted because included topics in stage 2 pulls excluded papers from stage 1 back into the result.

Through testing we have understood that Yewno is not a mature product (table 2) and still very much in development. A number of bugs and barriers to searching were identified during the testing process. Bugs include not being able to write in the notebook, not being able to save the notebook, the multi-select tool not working, refreshing the page deletes the research journey and previous search actions and missing bibliographic information in export. Likewise, but not tested intentionally during the think-aloud test, we discovered that the research journey is not always saved after one logs-out of the

system. Communication with Yewno about these bugs has been open and efficient. Bugs were quickly solved by the developers and in instances where the problem is ongoing, such as the notebook function, work arounds were suggested while the problem continues to be addressed.

Barriers to the search were primarily the design features of the Yewno interface rather than the way the search could be conducted. Test persons were frustrated with the laboriousness of having to mark every action, concept, document and map manually in the research journey in preparation for export. A missing function is a “select all” option in the research journey. Similarly, the research journey remembers all previous choices therefore a “reset/unselect” option is also missing. Another issue is that the delete option is dangerously close to the select option in the research journey and appears only during a mouse-over. As presented in the results section, the mouse over function on the knowledge maps that activates all relations was experienced as confusing and even blocked nodes so they could not be selected. Finally, the icons used on the interface were too small, dialogue from the system disappears too quickly, communication that the system is processing is too discrete and the colours used are not accessible to all users.

5.5 Added value to academic search for user groups

The test participants unanimously agreed that Iris.ai and Yewno are particularly suitable as a scoping or exploring tool for students and junior researchers at the beginning of a research project or at the end of a search to find supplementing or missed papers. One test person highlighted the “find related papers” in Iris.ai as a very valuable feature in and visualizing and analyzing the landscape surrounding a particular topic in Yewno made knowledge more accessible to the end-user. The map functionality was considered as the main value of Yewno. Presenting a visual representation of a topic that links seamlessly to literature was very useful in summarizing large document collections by their themes that could potentially reduce confusion and uncertainties at project start. As the test persons found their professionalism challenged in the two systems, they suggested that researchers might find Iris.ai and Yewno more efficient than information specialists, since the approach to searching is organic, instinctive and based on knowledge of a subject. However, how to document the search method has to be planned before the search with regards to intended publication (of the project).

For knowledge specialists, Yewno claims to save time, ensure comprehensive and credible coverage and help with communicating search strategies to end-users⁴. In the test setup it was not possible to investigate if Yewno saves time and the results of the think-aloud tests were critical of the usefulness of the communication of search strategies (sections 4.1.5, 4.2.5, and 5.3). However, both Iris.ai and Yewno search across multiple databases to define concepts and identify literature beneficially increasing the breadth and scope of the search. Both systems link to full text in the original publication. Therefore, the elements are in place to support source criticism and an efficient search across multiple databases rather than one database at a time (Beyer and Wright, 2012). It is the responsibility of the end-users to apply critical methods to identify the quality of the evidence. These aspects will be studied more in detail later on in the project (Hackathon, Autumn 2021).

5.6 Added value to academic search for information specialists

The Exploring tool was emphasized as looking good in Iris.ai. The information specialists liked the idea of exploring a new field with Iris.ai and maybe getting new ideas from the map. It was also called a “getting started tool” which potentially could add value to the work of the information specialists in the beginning of a search. The Focus tool was rated higher than the exploring tool however. The test-persons could see a logic in the way it was build. They could see a connection to the systematic search process and liked that

⁴ <https://www.yewno.com/education>

they were building on former choices. One information specialist was especially keen of the idea of Iris.ai searching in OA material which supports current research policy strategies.

The visual knowledge maps in Iris.ai and Yewno invited exploration and curiosity about a topic. The test persons used the maps to raise questions about the search case and possible new directions the search could go in that they could discuss with the researcher or student. They appreciated that the knowledge maps gave a quick overview of the topic and could see that these maps could be used in consultations with library users at the start of their research projects: both to delve deeper into a topic and discover new connections in the literature and also to narrow the search and define research questions. Regarding credibility, the test persons were critical of the quality and age of the text corpus as well as the comprehensiveness of the documentation of the search which typically would be communicated further to the end-user. One test person commented:

“One could never use such a search history [research journey] in a supervision situation. I would manually have to write down each step of the search, take snap shots of each action and describe why I did what I did.”

5.7 Supplement current service portfolio at KB

When testing Iris.ai we noticed quite an interest in the product from our colleagues. The focus on AI in society is high at the moment. The aspects of the technology and how it can be used in a university context are interesting and Iris.ai do have potential to become part of the portfolio at the University Libraries. It was a surprise for us that it requires so much time to learn how to search and use Iris.ai and it became clear to us that teaching and support in a system like Iris.ai requires personnel who can guide and help student and staff. Iris.ai and Yewno cannot stand alone as sources for searching literature. They have to be put into a search strategy that includes various databases related to the search case. This is best practice for literature research and nothing new, but must be communicated very clearly to library users. It is important to understand and to use Iris.ai and Yewno as the tools they are: not perfect, but useful supplements to searches for both students and researchers. The systems have the potential to contribute to innovation at the University since they suggest new directions in a research project (hypothesis generating) and because they can search a large corpus of multidisciplinary sources very quickly.

The use of AI-powered search systems have been suggested to supplement the students critical thinking and information literacy skills and are exemplified in the cases and curricula from universities and colleges⁵. The cases demonstrate using Yewno skills in inquiry and research in four skills areas: initiating and planning (particularly brainstorm and framing the research topic), performing and recording the search, analysing the retrieved content, interpreting and communicating the results of the search. Digital information literacy is joint focus area of the university library and the affiliated universities. Employing Iris.ai and Yewno feed directly into that strategy, enabling the individual student/researcher use state-of-the-art computational techniques and digital methods in their research. The test persons agreed that Iris.ai and Yewno are most useful at the start of a project, therefore potential use scenarios could be using the systems in a comprehensive search strategy similar to citation and reference seeking, or together with Scribo⁶ in an introduction to writing the bachelor or master thesis and developing a problem statement; in

⁵ <https://www.yewno.com/high-school>

⁶ <https://scribo.dk/en>

discussions with the contact librarian at the faculty library or as part of the “book an information specialist” service to explore a topic and define a direction for the project.

As such, Yewno was regarded as complimentary to the university library’s existing search tools and databases but was not considered a replacement for any other source in the library catalogue. Accordingly, the presentation of the systems is recommended as tools to support the exploratory phase of a research project. Instruction in the systems should be very thorough, including discussion of the algorithm, the quality of the sources, the functionalities, responsible conduct of research, how to document the search and relevant search standards and limitations of the system which is perhaps contradictory when considering the apparent ease in which searchers can get results out of the system and the inviting interface.

5.8 Improve discovery library catalogue

Iris.ai is an interesting tool – everyone agreed about that, but using it correctly, to get the best results and understand what’s going on “behind the scene” is difficult. Iris.ai does have some potential to add value to the portfolio of databases in the University Libraries, but it needs to be investigated further from the user perspective (this will be done in a Hackathon in Autumn 2021). Worth considering is merging some of the subscription databases with Iris.ai, to investigate how the algorithm works beyond the Open Access papers in CORE and PubMed, if access to sources is just as seamless and the effect including subscription sources could have on the perceived value of suggested concepts/topics and the search results.

Yewno can also be implemented as a widget in the library catalogue. The widget surfaces search suggestions from Yewno at the top of the results page in the catalogue. From here users can click through to explore the suggested topics using Yewno’s knowledge maps. Due to technical issues the widget was not available for testing during the think-aloud tests but will be tested in the Hackathon.

6. Limitations of the test set-up

Our test persons were all experienced in traditional database searching where a systematic approach is employed. It was difficult for them to abstract from this ingrained professionalism and not compare Iris.ai and Yewno to traditional block searching. They may have tried to make the AI-systems “fit” into their preconditioned approach to searching and consequently biased the tests. The test persons had very little experience using Iris.ai and Yewno. They had only participated in a 2-hour introductory workshop conducted by Iris.ai and Yewno consultants, although they were encouraged to watch a video made by the project group presenting the functionalities and search process in both systems and further encouraged to explore the systems independently with regard to their own subject expertise before the tests. Most of the test persons had no expertise in the search case used in the test. Accordingly, judgements of relevance were based on subjective assumptions rather than knowledge of the subject used in the case.

The test persons had step-by-step instructions to follow during the think-aloud tests. Each test person was provided with a print-out they could have next to them and a digital copy available for copy/pasting into the as a search statement in Iris.ai. We experienced that majority of the test persons stopped reading the instructions or skimmed each instruction very quickly and instead went on to discover the system on their own. We continually reminded them to stick to the instructions to ensure consistency in comparing search experiences and results of the test.

The quality of the retrieved documents was not assessed during the think-aloud test. We did not make pre-defined categories of quality. With quality we mean valuable and valid sources of information. These sources could be peer-reviewed journals or academic publishers. Quality could also be assessed with regards to the applied methodology in articles, but the test setup did not include time to assess the

methodological design in each verified article. Many of the test persons were not domain-experts in the field of our chosen case, so making this kind of quality assessment would be impossible.

7. Conclusions

In the think-aloud tests with information specialists Iris.ai and Yewno have proven to have potential to be part of the portfolio of databases at the university. Both could be suitable for students and PhD-students at the beginning of a project to explore a topic, generate ideas and discover unexpected cross-disciplinary perspectives on a topic. Further the systems could contribute to innovation at the university since they suggest new directions in a research project (hypothesis generating) and because they can search a large corpus of multidisciplinary sources very quickly. The systems are especially strong in providing a graphical view of a search that links seamlessly to literature. Particularly the systems are helpful to navigate in the growing amount of Open Access materials available and creating awareness of new sources of information. One of the main benefits of using Yewno is that it is a discovery tool rather than a search engine. It allows users to explore information across several disciplines in a simple way. However, in our test we observed that users got lost in all the cross-references and links between concepts and documents. Yewno does not support a transparent approach to the search and documentation of the discovery process is limited. Likewise, the quality of the literature corpus and relevance of retrieved documents requires further investigation. Quality is a parameter that will be tested in the up-coming Hackathon.

Iris.ai and Yewno complement the university library's existing search tools and databases but does not replace any other source in the library catalogue. Both systems do not support known item searching, but rather suggest potential directions and ways to explore a topic. The use of Iris.ai and Yewno requires thorough instruction and specialised support should be in system functionalities and in good literature research practices should be available. This service is recommended to include documenting new forms of academic search and source criticism. As both systems that come at considerable cost and only supplement other scholarly databases the question remains what the return on investment will be and how this can be evaluated.

In conclusion, Iris.ai and Yewno are effective tools to explore a topic but not an efficient, transparent or reliable academic search tool.

8. Next steps

- Test Iris.ai and Yewno with users (researchers and students) using a cross disciplinary case to further assess the usefulness of the systems for different user groups from different disciplines (Autumn 2021).
 - Ensure in the test setup to assess quality of retrieved papers. Quality will be assessed as methodological quality, relevance to topic and authority of the paper/source.
 - Explore further how to responsibly document and save searches conducted in Iris.ai and Yewno
 - Compare the efficiency of Iris.ai and Yewno to users preferred databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of Science, etc.
 - Compare the added value of Iris.ai and Yewno to other discovery tools, e.g. Open Knowledge Maps, Keenious, etc.
 - Test the Yewno widget in the university library catalogue.
 - Investigate and flag recurring technical issues that effect the reliability and stability of Iris.ai and Yewno.

- Assess the overall value of Iris.ai and Yewno for users and information specialists. Recommend possible license cancellation or renewal for one or both of the systems (January 2022).
- Suggest potential support services from the library, including instruction in the Iris.ai and Yewno, teaching discovery search techniques, documenting the search and methodological choices (March 2022).
 - Support in source criticism for teaching and conducting discovery search.
 - Challenges and opportunities for finding high-quality evidence in discovery systems.
 - Best guidance for students, researchers and information specialist for identifying reliable sources of information and the best available evidence to answer their questions
 - Information literacy and critical appraisal skills that enable responsible literature search practices
 - Transparency of AI-powered search (algorithms, reproducibility, reliability)
- Argue for the placement of the AI-powered search system in the KB infrastructure: Biblioteksservice & Partnere (KUB, Rub, AUL) [*Library Service and Partnerships, Copenhagen University Library, Roskilde University Library and Aarhus University Library*], Afdelingen for Bibliotekssystem [*The Department of Library Systems*], Afdeling for Licensforvaltning [*Department of License Negotiation*] and KB Digital [*Department of Digitalisation at the Royal Library, Denmark*]. (March 2022)

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Appendix 2: Case and problem statement

Problem statement and definition of research task issued to all participants.

COVID-19: Interdisciplinary perspectives on the Pandemic

As the COVID-19 outbreak expanded across the globe, researchers in both the medical and health sciences, natural and technical sciences, social sciences and humanities shared timely insight meant to enlighten all sectors of society. Until recently, communications technology infrastructure and system innovation were looked on as a luxury in many parts of the world. The Covid-19 pandemic has created another reality. Not only have governments adopted the use of digital technologies to confront the pandemic and address a wide range of pandemic-related issues, but they have also supported the survival and continuity of vital sectors in our lives, such as education, which suddenly took advantage of whatever infrastructure it had to reach billions of students stranded. National health authorities, pharmaceutical companies, universities, and research institutes worked together to find therapies to save lives and contain the social and economic consequences of the pandemic. Other sectors turned to online solutions, new digital devices and technologies. Cloud computing, data analytics, artificial intelligence, and other emerging technologies offered benefits for ultrafast innovation, sharing information and collectively creating knowledge. Machine learning coupled with big data rapidly identified links between needs and solutions. Technology has indeed proven its worth in running affairs when almost all physical mobility stopped. The situation has provided an eye-opening motivation to boost collaboration around technology development and infrastructures to serve humanity.

What it means to “innovate” has been redefined. The conventional approach to innovation in the pharmaceutical industry for example is to conduct a lengthy process that starts with the discovery and generation of potential drug compounds and moves through a meticulous refinement and selection phase toward gradual development, clinical testing, and market approval. This approach is now complemented with an ultrafast approach to innovation centered on the repurposing of readily available ideas from different stakeholders, knowledge, and technologies.

There are some important questions we can pose to the redefinition of innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration in finding solutions. In this fictional research project, you are asked to review the literature regarding the following four questions. Formulate a search statement for one or more questions and investigate the theme from your own disciplinary perspective:

1. What lessons can we learn from rapid innovation from Covid 19 pandemic?
2. What relevance has the redefinition of innovation have for the university? The way we teach, we learn, the way we do research?
3. Which fields have worked together in interdisciplinary innovations to find Covid 19 solutions?
4. What is the importance of interdisciplinary approaches for current challenges and those they lay a head?

Appendix 3: Hackathon pre-survey

Kære alle

Igen tak fordi du vil deltage i AI- Hackathon på mandag.

Vi håber du vil tage dig tid til at svare på dette korte spørgeskema om baggrundsoplysninger.

Dine svar behandles strengt fortroligt. Vi vil selvfølgelig ikke bruge navnet på de enkelte besvarelser og oplysningerne vil blive anonymiseret

Thank you so much for participating in AI- Hackathon.

We hope you will take the time to answer a short pre-survey. Your answers will be handled confidentially.

Mvh

Lorna Wildgaard (lowi@kb.dk)

Julie Kiersgaard (juki@kb.dk)

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Anne Vils Møller (anvm@kb.dk)

1: Hvad er dit navn? / What is your name?

2. Hvilket uddannelsesniveau/titel har du? / Which educational level/title do you hold?

3. Hvad er dit fagområde? / What is your area of expertise?

4. Hvad er din erfaring med systematisk søgning og review processen? / What is your experience with systematic literature search and the review process?

Definition: Systematisk søgning og reviews benytter sig af den systematiske og transparente tilgang til identifikation og kvalitetsvurdering af litteratur. Dvs. du laver en grundig afsøgning af den videnskabelige litteratur inden for et bestemt felt på en struktureret og systematisk måde, og evt. anvender etablerede standarder for søgeprotokoller og afrapportering. Formålet er ofte at kortlægge, hvad der er skrevet om en problemstilling.

Definition: Systematic searching and reviews employ a systematic and transparent approach to identification and quality assessment of literature. This is a thorough search of the scientific literature concerning a specific field, performed in a structured and systematic way e.g. with the use of standardised search protocols and reporting standards. The goal is often to map out what is written about a certain problem statement.

5. Hvilke online værktøjer (gerne 3 eller flere) anvender du oftest til at finde forskningsartikler og bøger? (f.eks. Google, Google Scholar, Pubmed, bibliotekskataloget, JSTOR, Psycinfo osv.) / Which online tools (3 or more) do you often use to find scientific literature (e.g. Google, Google Scholar, Pubmed, JSTOR, Psycinfo, the library catalogue)?

6. Hvordan vil du vurdere dine evner for at udføre systematiske søgninger? / How would you rate your systematic searching abilities?

- (1) Ekspert / [Expert](#)
- (2) God / [Good](#)
- (3) Nogenlunde/ [Intermediate](#)
- (4) Begynder / [Novice](#)

7. Hvor meget erfaring har du i at søge med Iris.ai/Yewno discover? / How much experience do you have in searching with Iris.ai/Yewno discover?

Tusind tak for hjælpen / [Thank you very much](#)

Appendix 4: Observation template

Observation template

1. Descriptions (fill out while observing)	
Facts	<i>Date, group demographics (age, sex, academic seniority), time</i>
Physical environment	<i>Describe location, interior design, sound conditions, audio/visual aids</i>
Activities	<i>Describe the actions of the observed participants. Pay attention to the interaction between the participants. Who interacts with whom? How do they interact with the system? What is the normal search behaviour? In which situations do they deviate from this behaviour? Pay attention to body language, frustration and behaviour.</i>
Objects	<i>Describe objects of interest for this project. Case understanding, Translation of the case in the system (search terms), Search behavior – maps and concepts, Clarification, Efficiency, Screening, Relevance assessment, Documentation, Export, System understanding.</i>
Questions	<i>Questions, praise and critique from the participants.</i>
Culture/values	<i>What do you observe about rules, attitudes, opinions, habits, values, and traditions concerning the academic search process? Does the group adhere to a set of values when searching in the AI-system?</i>
Interpretations	
Surprises	<i>Describe surprising observations: E.g....."if there are many pages of results, is there a tendency to only read the first two pages" – "It surprised us that the youngest participants were really good at reading the help pages to be able operate the system, whereas the senior participants tried out the system without reading the instructions."</i>
Observer role	<i>Reflect on your preconceptions, and whether your role as an observer has affected the observed participants in the observed situation. E.g. – "We had a preconception that the senior participants were better at designing a search". - "The fact that we were observing the search could have made the participants work faster than they usually would have."</i>
Other comments	<i>Comments and reflections during the observation. Ideas for analysis.</i>

Appendix 5: Reflection document Yewno

Refleksionsdokument / Reflection document

I dette dokument bedes I dokumentere trinene i jeres søgeprocess samt beskrive og forklare jeres valg.

Gennem hele søgningen bedes I tage snapshots af de "maps" I skaber for at gemme dem i "journey". Definitionerne på de "concepts" I vælger bliver automatisk gemt i "journey"

De dokumenter som ser relevante ud, skal markeres med en stjerne så de kan gemmes i "Journey".

Når I er tilfredse med resultatet bedes I eksportere:

- Gem "Journey" (snapshots af "knowledge maps", "concept" definitioner og stjerne-markerede dokumenter) til din Google Drive. Upload en kopi til Google Drive

Screening af resultatet

Udvælg i gruppen de (max 10) mest relevante dokumenter. Udfyld rapportformularen, som I finder i Google mappen. Udfyld venligst DOI/ URL for hvert dokument korrekt

In this document you are asked to document your steps in the search and provide a rationale for what you did and why. This is the logbook for your search

Throughout the search, please take snapshots of the maps you create to save them to the "journey". Remember to "star" documents you consider interesting. These together with definitions of the concepts you searched, will be saved in the Journey.

When you are satisfied with a search, please export:

The journey (snap shots of maps, starred documents and concept definitions) to your Google Drive. Please upload a copy of the export to Google Drive.

Screening the results

Decide within the group which (maximum) 10 documents are the most relevant. Fill out the evaluation form, found in the group's Google Folder. Please ensure the DOI/url for each document is correct.

1. Diskussion af case/ Discussion of the case

Her bedes I notere jeres indledende og fortløbende diskussion af casen. Beskriv overvejelser, tanker og justeringer undervejs i søgeprocessen.

In this section, record your preliminary and on-going discussion of the case. Outline any considerations, thoughts or adjustments you make throughout the search process.

2. Forskningsspørgsmål/ Research question:

Skriv jeres forskningsspørgsmål her (gerne flere hvis det er relevant) /Write you research question(s) in this section. Note each research question you work with.

3. Kommentarer til forskningsspørgsmål /Comments on the research question

Hvordan oversætter I forskningsspørgsmål til søgning. Beskriv jeres forståelse af målet med søgningen, endpoints, omfang og rationale for søgning, etc. / How you translate the research question into a search. Note your understanding of the aim of the search, endpoints, scope and objectives, etc.

4. Begreber identificerede i forskningsspørgsmålet /Concepts and attributes identified in research question

For hvert forskningsspørgsmål du arbejder med, notér hvilke begreber der er identificeret. Hvilke egenskaber har begreberne som skal yderligere defineres i søgningen? /For each research question, write the concepts and attributes you identify in the research question

5. Koncepter oversat til definitioner i Yewno og hvordan I søgte og kombinerede dem /Concepts translated to definitions in Yewno and how you searched and combined them

Koncepter og definitioner: Noter om "Concepts" i Yewno "passer" til de koncepter I har identificeret i forskningsspørgsmålet og formålet med søgningen. Er de specifikke nok? Var I nødt til at gå på kompromis eller gentænke søgestrategien / Concepts and definition: Note if the concepts in Yewno "fit" the concepts identified in the research question and the aim of the search. Do they provide a good fit? not specific enough? Did you have to compromise and rethink the search strategy?

6. Filters applied

Noter hvilke filtre du anvender og om de hjælper dig i din søgeproces.

Please note which filters you applied and if they help you in the search process

7. Journey (søgehistorik) / Journey (search history)

“Journey” dokumenterer din søgning. Mens du søger bedes du tage snapshots af de maps du gerne vil beholde samt stjernemarkere favoritdokumenter. Sammen med “Concepts” vil disse blive gemt i Journey. Du kan eksportere “Journey” til Google docs, RIS eller CSV. Noter her om Journey lever op til dine forventninger til dokumentation af søgning / The Journey is a place to document your search. While you search, take snapshots of the maps you want to keep and “star” documents as favourites. This, together with concept definitions, will be saved in the Journey. You can export information saved in the journey to Google Docs, RIS or CSV. In this section note if the Journey meets your expectations to documenting a search.

8. Evaluer din søgning / Evaluate your search

Som regel udføres flere søgninger da den første søgning enten giver for mange, for få eller for irrelevante resultater. Hvordan vil I evaluere jeres søgning? Hvis I ønsker at lave en ny søgning gå til sektion 9.

Hvis I er tilfredse med søgninger, gå til sektion 10.

You usually have to carry out more than one search, as the initial search often generates either too few or too many results. You may also find that too many of the articles are not relevant to your topic. How would you evaluate the search? If you wish to conduct another search, return to your research question and make the necessary changes to your search. Move on to section 9.

If you are satisfied with the search, continue to section 10.

9. Lav søgningen igen / Perform the search again

Lav søgningen igen med de rettelse I lavede i sektion 6. Beskriv kort hvordan I lavede søgningerne. Er I tilfredse med resultatet ?

Perform the search again with the changes you have made in Section 8. Please give a short description of how you conducted the search in Yewno. Note where you felt Yewno supported your search process as well as points of frustration. Are you satisfied with the results?

10. Describe the search process in Yewno

Giv en kort beskrivelse af hvordan du greb søgningen an i Yewno. Brugte du multi-select funktionen, udforskede layers og snippets. Notér hvordan du oplevede at søge i Yewno (positive oplevelser og frustrationer). Er du tilfreds med resultatet? Please give a short description of how you conducted the search in Yewno. Did you use the multi-select function, explore layers and snippets? Note where you felt Yewno supported your search process as well as points of frustration. Are you satisfied with the results?

11. Udfyld rapportformularen/ Fill out the report form

Appendix 6: Reflection document Iris.ai

Refleksionsdokument / Reflection document

I dette dokument bedes I dokumentere trinene i jeres søgeprocess samt beskrive og forklare jeres valg.

Gennem hele søgningen bedes I gemme de "knowledge maps" I skaber i "Exploring". Gem dem i ORGANIZATION STUDIES. Det samme gør sig gældende for Step 1-2-3 i Focus Tool, her bedes I ligeledes gemme i ORGANIZATION STUDIES løbende.

Navngiv jeres filer ensartet!

Fx. "hackathon_gruppe1_søgningsnummer_[dine initialer]"

Når I er tilfredse med resultatet bedes I gemme:

- Exploring Knowledge map
- Focus Studies

Screening af resultatet

Udvælg i gruppen de (max 10) mest relevante dokumenter. Udfyld rapportformularen, som I finder i Google mappen. Udfyld venligst DOI/ URL for hvert dokument korrekt.

In this document you are asked to document your steps in the search and provide a rationale for what you did and why. This is the logbook for your search

Throughout the search, please save the "knowledge maps" you create in the "Exploring tool". Save them in ORGANIZATION STUDIES. Do the same for Step 1-2-3 in the "Focus Tool".

Name your files consistently.

E.g. "Hackathon_group1_searchnumber_[your initials]"

When you are happy with the result, please save:

- Exploring Knowledge map
- Focus Studies

Screening the results

Decide within the group which (maximum) 10 documents are the most relevant. Fill out the evaluation form, found in the group's Google Folder. Please ensure the DOI/url for each document is correct.

1. Diskussion af case/ Discussion of the case

Her bedes I notere jeres indledende og fortløbende diskussion af casen. Beskriv overvejelser, tanker og justeringer undervejs i søgeprocessen.

In this section, record your preliminary and on-going discussion of the case. Outline any considerations, thoughts or adjustments you make throughout the search process.

2. Forskningsspørgsmål/ Research question:

Skriv jeres forskningsspørgsmål her (gerne flere hvis det er relevant) /Write you research question(s) in this section. Note each research question you work with.

3. Kommentarer til forskningsspørgsmål /Comments on the research question

Hvordan oversætter I forskningsspørgsmål til søgning. Beskriv jeres forståelse af målet med søgningen, endpoints, omfang og rationale for søgning, etc. / How you translate the research question into a search. Note your understanding of the aim of the search, endpoints, scope and objectives, etc.

4. Begreber identificerede i forskningsspørgsmålet /Concepts and attributes identified in research question

For hvert forskningsspørgsmål du arbejder med, notér hvilke begreber der er identificeret. Hvilke egenskaber har begreberne som skal yderligere defineres i søgningen? /For each research question, write the concepts and attributes you identify in the research question

5. Søgning / Search

Søg i Iris.ai og copy/paste problem statement eller URL ind her./ Search in Iris.ai and Copy/paste the problem statement or URL here

6. Filtre du anvender / Filters

Noter hvilke filtre du anvender og om de hjælper dig i din søgeproces. / Please note which filters you applied and if they help you in the search process

7. Lav og gem dit knowledge map i Organizational Studies (search history) / Create and save your knowledge map in Organizational Studies (search history)

Organizational Studies er her I kan gemme jeres Knowledge map og Fokus studie. / You can save your Knowledge maps and Focus studies in Organizational studies

8. Focus tool

Fokus tool er bygget op om 3 stadier. Imens du fokuserer dit studie, notér observationer her. Fx: Hvilke koncepter og emner bruger du? Hvor effektiv er din søgning? / *Focus tool consists of 3 stages. While you focus your studie, note observations here. E.g. Which concepts and topics do you use? How efficient is your search?*

Efter stadie 3 kan du eksportere din søgning til Excel eller CSV.

Noter her om muligheden for at dokumentere din søgning er tilstrækkelig i forhold til dine forventninger. / *After stage 3, export your search to Excel or CSV. Please note whether the documentation options live up to your expectations.*

9. Evaluer din søgning / Evaluate your search

Som regel udføres flere søgninger da den første søgning enten giver for mange, for få eller for irrelevante resultater. Hvordan vil I evaluere jeres søgning? Hvis I ønsker at lave en ny søgning gå til sektion 7.

Hvis I er tilfredse med søgninger, gå til sektion 11.

You usually have to carry out more than one search, as the initial search often generates either too few or too many results. You may also find that too many of the articles are not relevant to your topic. How would you evaluate the search? If you wish to conduct another search, return to your research question and make the necessary changes to your search. Move on to section 7.

If you are satisfied with the search, continue to section 11.

10. Lav søgningen igen / Perform the search again

Lav søgningen igen med de rettelse I lavede i sektion 6. Beskriv kort hvordan I lavede søgningerne. Er I tilfredse med resultatet ?

Perform the search again with the changes you have made in Section 7. Please give a short description of how you conducted the search in Yewno. Note where you felt Yewno supported your search process as well as points of frustration. Are you satisfied with the results?

11. Beskriv søgeprocessen in Iris.ai / Describe the search process in Iris.ai

Giv en kort beskrivelse af hvordan du greb søgningen an i Iris.ai. Brugte du filtre eller Edit map. Notér hvordan du oplevede at søge i Iris.ai (positive oplevelser og frustrationer). Er du tilfreds med resultatet? Please give a short description of how you conducted the search in Iris.ai. Did you use filters or did you edit your map. Note where you felt lirs.ai supported your search process as well as points of frustration. Are you satisfied with the results?

12. Udfyld rapportformularen/ Fill out the report form

Appendix 7: Reflection document PubMed - Google Scholar - WOS

Refleksionsdokument / Reflection document

I dette dokument bedes I dokumentere trinene i jeres søgeprocess samt beskrive og forklare jeres valg.

Når I er tilfredse med resultatet bedes I eksportere/ kopi/paste:

- Søgestrengen fra de enkelte databaser til dette dokument, nedenstående punkter

Screening af resultatet

Udvælg i gruppen de (max 10) mest relevante dokumenter. Udfyld rapportformularen, som I finder i Google mappen. Udfyld venligst DOI/ URL for hvert dokument korrekt

In this document you are asked to document your steps in the search and provide a rationale for what you did and why. This is the logbook for your search

When you are happy with the result, please export / copy/paste:

- The search string from each database to this document, see below.

Screening the results

Decide within the group which (maximum) 10 documents are the most relevant. Fill out the evaluation form, found in the group's Google Folder. Please ensure the DOI/url for each document is correct.

1. Diskussion af case/ Discussion of the case

Her bedes I notere jeres indledende og fortløbende diskussion af casen. Beskriv overvejelser, tanker og justeringer undervejs i søgeprocessen.

In this section, record your preliminary and on-going discussion of the case. Outline any considerations, thoughts or adjustments you make throughout the search process.

2. Forskningsspørgsmål/ Research question:

Skriv jeres forskningsspørgsmål her (gerne flere hvis det er relevant) /Write you research question(s) in this section. Note each research question you work with.

3. Kommentarer til forskningsspørgsmål /Comments on the research question

Hvordan oversætter I forskningsspørgsmål til søgning. Beskriv jeres forståelse af målet med søgningen, endpoints, omfang og rationale for søgning, etc. / How you translate the research question into a search. Note your understanding of the aim of the search, endpoints, scope and objectives, etc.

4. Søgning / Search

Søg i nedenstående databaser / [Search in the databases](#)

4.1 Pubmed

Blok 1	Blok 2	Blok 3	Blok 4
MeSH:	MeSH:	MeSH:	MeSH:
<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>	<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>	<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>	<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>

4.1.1 Kontrollerede emneord / [controlled vocabulary](#):

Beskriv og forklar valg af MESH termer / [Describe and explain the use of MeSH terms](#)

4.1.2 Fritekstord / [free text terms](#):

Beskriv og forklar valg af fritekstord samt hvilke felter der søges i. / [Describe and explain the use of free text terms and field codes](#)

4.1.3 Filtre / [Filters](#):

Beskriv og forklar evt. anvendte filtre / [Describe and explain the use of filters](#)

4.1.4 Endelig søgestreng / [Final search string](#)

kopi paste din endelige søgestreng her / [Copy/paste your final search string here](#):

4.2 Google scholar

4.2.1 Fritekstord/ [Free text terms](#):

Beskriv og forklar valg af søgeord. Hvis du brugte avanceret søgning, kopi/paste formularen her / [Describe and explain the choice og search terms. whether you used advanced search, copy/paste the string here:](#)

4.2.2 Filtre / [Filters](#):

Beskriv og forklar evt. anvendte filtre / [Describe and explain the use of filters](#)

4.2.3 Endelig søgestreng / [Final search string](#)

kopi paste din endelige søgestreng her / [Copy/paste your final search string here:](#)

4.3 Web of Science

4.3.1 Fritekstord / [free text terms](#):

Beskriv og forklar valg af fritekstord samt hvilke felter der søges i./ [Describe and explain the use of free text terms and field codes](#)

4.3.2 Filtre / [Filters](#):

Beskriv og forklar evt. anvendte filtre / [Describe and explain the use of filters](#)

Blok 1	Blok 2	Blok 3	Blok 4
<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>	<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>	<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>	<i>Fritekst: (angiv hvilke felter der søges i) Free text terms (please note any field codes used)</i>

4.3.3 Endelig søgestreng / [Final search string](#)

kopi paste din endelige søgestreng her / [Copy/paste your final search string here:](#)

5. Evaluer din søgning / Evaluate your search

Som regel udføres flere søgninger da den første søgning enten giver for mange, for få eller for irrelevante resultater. Hvordan vil I evaluere jeres søgning? Hvis I ønsker at lave en ny søgning gå til sektion 6.

Hvis I er tilfredse med søgninger, gå til sektion 7.

You usually have to carry out more than one search, as the initial search often generates either too few or too many results. You may also find that too many of the articles are not relevant to your topic. How would you evaluate the search? If you wish to conduct another search, return to your research question and make the necessary changes to your search. Move on to section 7.

If you are satisfied with the search, continue to section 11.

6. Lav søgningen igen / Perform the search again

Lav søgningen igen med de rettelse I lavede i sektion 6. Beskriv kort hvordan I lavede søgningerne. Er I tilfredse med resultatet ?

Perform the search again with the changes you have made in Section 7. Please give a short description of how you conducted the search in Yewno. Note where you felt Yewno supported your search process as well as points of frustration. Are you satisfied with the results?

12. Udfyld rapportformularen/ Fill out the report form

Appendix 8: Report form for literature search results

Rapportformular for søgeresultatet / Report form for literature search results

Alle grupper bedes dokumentere op til 10 udvalgte publikationer ved hjælp af nedenstående rapportformular. Brug venligst en rapport for hvert forskningsspørgsmål.

Eksperter med viden om det stillede forskningsspørgsmål vil efterfølgende evaluere og rangere søgeresultatet i forhold videnskabelig kvalitet ved brug af en standardiseret evalueringsformular.

All groups are asked to document up to 10 chosen publications using a standardized report form. Please use one report form per research question searched.

A committee of experts with backgrounds related to the posed research question will evaluate and rank the search results according to scientific quality and quantity criteria using a standardized scoring sheet.

Forskningsspørgsmål / Research Question					
Nr./no	Publikations titel / Paper title	Bidrag til forskning / Contribution type facet	Forskningstype/ Research type facet	Publikationens konklusion/ Paper conclusions	Publikationens ID / URL / Paper ID / URL
	Publikationens fulde titel / <i>Please provide the full paper title</i>	Hvilke specifikke elementer handler publikationen om / <i>What specific element does the paper relate to?</i>	Hvilken forskningstype bliver beskrevet i publikationen / <i>What aspect of research is the paper about?</i>	Beskriv venligst publikationens hovedbudskaber / <i>Please provide the paper's key conclusion</i>	Publikationens unikke ID / DOI/ URL / <i>Please provide a unique paper ID, DOI or URL</i>
	Indsæt titlen / Insert full title below	Beskriv det relevante element: metodologi, metrik, prototype, process/model, teori, intervention, eller andet (uddyb). / Select below one of: related to a methodology, related to a metric, related to a prototype, related to a process/model, related to a theory, related to an intervention, other (please elaborate).	Beskriv forskningstypen: validering, evaluering, løsningsforslag, filosofisk artikel, meningsartikel, eller andet. / Select below one of: validation research, evaluation research, solution proposal, philosophical paper, opinion paper, experience paper, other.	Beskriv jeres opfattelse af publikationens konklusioner / Insert your take on the paper's key take-aways below.	Indsæt unikt ID / Insert unique ID below.

1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					

Appendix 9: Hackathon Post-survey Iris.ai

Post-interview AI hackathon

November 2021

Mange tak for din deltagelse i AI- Hackathon.

Som evaluering og opsamling håber vi du vil svare på nedenstående spørgeskema, hvor vi gerne vil afdække din holdning, oplevelser og adfærd i systemet.

Dine svar behandles strengt fortroligt.

Vi vil selvfølgelig ikke bruge navnet på de enkelte besvarelser og oplysningerne vil blive anonymiseret.

Thank you very much for your participation in AI-Hackathon.

As an evaluation, we hope you will answer this questionnaire, where we would like to uncover your experiences and behavior in the system.

Your answers will be treated with confidence.

Of course, we will not use the name of the individual answers and the information will be anonymised.

Lorna Wildgaard (lowi@kb.dk)

Julie K. Lyngsfeldt (juki@kb.dk)

Anne Vils Møller (anvm@kb.dk)

Solveig Johnsen (ssjo@kb.dk)

Dit navn / Your name

Fortæl med dine egne ord, hvad formålet med Iris.ai er / Tell in your own words what the purpose of Iris.ai is

Hvordan vil du vurdere din overordnede oplevelse af Iris.ai (1 = lavest tilfredshed)?
/ How would you rate your overall experience of Iris.ai (1 = lowest rate)?

- (1) 1
- (2) 2
- (3) 3
- (4) 4
- (5) 5

Uddyb dit svar / Please elaborate on your answer

Betragter du søgning i Iris.ai som en effektiv måde at udforske et emne på? / Do you consider searching in Iris.ai as an effective way to explore a topic?

Betragter du søgning i Iris.ai som en effektiv måde at søge litteratur på? / Do you consider searching in Iris.ai is an effective way to search literature?

Understøtter Iris.ai måden at søge systematisk på? / Does Iris.ai support the systematic way of searching?

- (1) Ja / yes
- (2) Tildels /Partly
- (5) Nej / no
- (3) Det ved jeg ikke / I don't know

Uddyb dit svar / Please elaborate on your answer

Levede Iris.ai op til din forventning i forhold til kvaliteten af de artikler du har fremfundet? / Did Iris.ai live up to your expectations in terms of the quality of the articles you have found?

- (1) Ja / [yes](#)
- (2) Tildels / [Partly](#)
- (5) Nej / [no](#)
- (3) Det ved jeg ikke / [I don't know](#)

Uddyb dit svar / Please elaborate on your answer

Hvor veldokumenteret synes du dit arbejde i Iris.ai er? / How well-documented do you think your work in Iris.ai is?

Vil du anvende Iris.ai igen? (hvorfor/hvorfor ikke?) / Do you want to use Iris.ai again? (why/why not?)

Kan du se Iris.ai som en del af din forsknings eller undervisningsportefølje? (forklar hvorfor/hvorfor ikke?) / Can you see Iris.ai as part of your research or teaching portfolio? (explain why/why not?)

**På hvilket uddannelsesniveau (bachelor, kandidat, ph.d.) ser du værdien af
anvendelse af Iris.ai? / At what level of education (bachelor, master, PhD) do you
see the value of using Iris.ai?**

Tusind tak for hjælpen!

Thank you for your help!

Appendix 10: Hackathon Post-survey Yewno

Post-interview AI hackathon

November 2021

Mange tak for din deltagelse i AI- Hackathon.

Som evaluering og opsamling håber vi du vil svare på nedenstående spørgeskema, hvor vi gerne vil afdække din holdning, oplevelser og adfærd i systemet.

Dine svar behandles strengt fortroligt.

Vi vil selvfølgelig ikke bruge navnet på de enkelte besvarelser og oplysningerne vil blive anonymiseret.

Thank you very much for your participation in AI-Hackathon.

As an evaluation, we hope you will answer this questionnaire, where we would like to uncover your experiences and behavior in the system.

Your answers will be treated with confidence.

Of course, we will not use the name of the individual answers and the information will be anonymised.

Lorna Wildgaard (lowi@kb.dk)

Julie K. Lyngsfeldt (juki@kb.dk)

Anne Vils Møller (anvm@kb.dk)

Solveig Johnsen (ssjo@kb.dk)

Dit navn / Your name

Fortæl med dine egne ord, hvad formålet med Yewno er / Tell in your own words what the purpose of Yewno is

Hvordan vil du vurdere din overordnede oplevelse af Yewno (1 = lavest tilfredshed)? / How would you rate your overall experience of Yewno (1 = lowest rate)?

- (1) 1
- (2) 2
- (3) 3
- (4) 4
- (5) 5

Uddyb dit svar / Please elaborate on your answer

Betragter du søgning i Yewno som en effektiv måde at udforske et emne på? / Do you consider searching in Yewno as an effective way to explore a topic?

Betragter du søgning i Yewno som en effektiv måde at søge litteratur på? / Do you consider searching in Yewno is an effective way to search literature?

Understøtter Yewno måden at søge systematisk på? / Does the system support Yewno way of searching?

- (1) Ja / yes
- (2) Tildels / Partly
- (4) Nej / no
- (3) Det ved jeg ikke / I don't know

Uddyb dit svar / Please elaborate on your answer

Levede Yewno op til din forventning i forhold til kvaliteten af de artikler du har fremfundet? / Did Yewno live up to your expectations in terms of the quality of the articles you have found?

- (1) Ja / yes
- (2) Tildels / Partly
- (4) Nej / no
- (3) Det ved jeg ikke / I don't know

Uddyb dit svar / Please elaborate on your answer

Hvor veldokumenteret synes du dit arbejde i Yewno er (begrund gerne)? / How well-documented do you think your work in Yewno is (please explain why/why not)?

Vil du anvende Yewno igen? (hvorfor/hvorfor ikke?) / Do you want to use Yewno again? (why/why not?)

Kan du se Yewno som en del af din forsknings eller undervisningsportefølje? (forklar hvorfor/hvorfor ikke?) / Can you see Yewno as part of your research or teaching portfolio? (explain why/why not?)

**På hvilket uddannelsesniveau (bachelor, kandidat, ph.d.) ser du værdien af
anvendelse af Yewno? / At what level of education (bachelor, master, PhD) do you
see the value of using Yewno?**

Tusind tak for hjælpen!

Thank you for your help!

Appendix 11: Expert assessment survey

Thank you for helping us assess the articles found in the AI Hackathon.

1. Which educational level/title do you hold?

2. What is your area of expertise?

3. Please write down the title of the article you are reviewing

4. How much can the results in the article be trusted? Please comment.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
(lowest score)									(highest score)

Comments:

5. How much can you trust the conclusions? Please comment.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
(lowest score)									(highest score)

Comments:

6. Please paste in the research question from the Hackathon:

7. Do you consider the article to answer the research question from the Hackathon? (Please answer relevant, not relevant or partially relevant)

- (1) Relevant
- (2) Partially relevant
- (3) Not relevant

Comments:

8. Do you consider the article to be “spot-on” in relevance regarding the research questions from the Hackathon? (yes/no)

- (1) Yes
- (2) No

Comments:

Thank you very much for your help!

Mvh

Lorna Wildgaard (lowi@kb.dk)

Julie Kiersgaard (juki@kb.dk)

Anne Vils Møller (anvm@kb.dk)

Solveig Johnsen (ssjo@kb.dk)